

Mannich Reaction. N-[2-Hydroxy-3 (or 5 or 6)-Substituted] Benzyl Glycines

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Some N-[2-hydroxy-3 (or 5 or 6)-substituted] benzyl glycines have been prepared by condensing phenols with formaldehyde and glycine in the presence of sodium acetate and acetic acid. Their constitutions established by alkylation followed by oxidation and identifying the resultant acids.

THE condensation between formaldehyde, ammonia or a primary or secondary amine (usually as the hydrochloride) and a compound containing at least one active hydrogen is described as Mannich Reaction. Schwarzenbach and Anderegg¹ and Temkina² *et al.* used a Mannich type of reaction for introducing $-\text{CH}_2\text{N}(\text{CH}_2\text{COOH})_2$ group at positions ortho to a phenolic group under alkaline conditions. Pribil and Korbl³ have described a similar reaction in acetic acid medium. Korbl and Svoboda⁴ described a patent for the preparation of sodium salts of N-(*o*-hydroxy benzyl) iminodiacetic acid and N-(*o*-hydroxy benzyl) glycines. However, the information on preparation and characterisation of N-[2-hydroxy-3 (or 5 or 6)-substituted] benzyl glycines (III) is scanty and incomplete. A systematic programme of work on the preparation of these compounds has now been undertaken.

For the preparation of (III), an intimate mixture of equimolecular amounts of phenol (I), glycine and sodium acetate in an excess of acetic acid was treated with calculated amount of formaldehyde solution at 60°-80°. The sodium salt of N-[2-hydroxy 3- (or 5 or 6)-substituted] benzyl glycines (II) was precipitated

from alcohol, dissolved in a little H₂O and the free acid (III) precipitated with dil. HCl. Hydroxy benzoic acids were employed as their sodium salts.

The constitution of (III) was established by converting these into their methyl derivatives (IV), and oxidising the latter to the corresponding methoxy derivatives of benzoic acids, phthalic acid and iso-phthalic acids(V).

Experimental

Preparation of N-[2-hydroxy-3(or 5 or 6)-substituted] benzyl glycines (III) :

0.5 mole of phenol, 37.5 g (0.5 mole) of glycine (dried at 100° for 2 hrs.), 68 g (0.5 mole) of sodium acetate crystals and 250 ml of acetic acid were taken in a beaker. To this 45 ml of formalin (36%) was added dropwise with stirring. The temperature was gradually raised to 60° till a homogeneous solution was obtained. Heating and occasional stirring was continued for further 2 hrs, keeping the temperature between 60°-80°. The mixture was allowed to cool to room temperature, and diluted with ethanol

X, Y = H, CH₃, Cl, COOH

TABLE 1

No.	Compound	Yield %	Colour	m.p.* °C	found			calculated		
					C	H	N	C	H	N
1.	2,OH,BzG	38.67	white	218	59.50	6.20	7.80	59.66	6.07	7.73
2.	2,OH,3,CH ₃ ,BzG	46.15	white	sint. 152 melt. 172	61.68	6.60	7.00	61.53	6.66	7.18
3.	2,OH,5,CH ₃ ,BzG	51.28	white	203 d	61.29	6.85	7.09	61.53	6.66	7.18
4.	2,OH,6,CH ₃ ,BzG	48.24	dirty white	above 360	61.63	6.53	7.35	61.53	6.66	7.18
5.	3,Cl,2,OH,BzG	51.13	faint yellow	210 d	50.30	4.79	6.60	50.11	4.64	6.49
6.	5,Cl,2,OH,BzG	49.18	white	164	50.00	4.80	6.33	50.11	4.64	6.49
7.	5,Cl,2,OH,6,CH ₃ ,BzG	49.67	dirty yellow	200 d	52.10	5.20	6.05	52.29	5.22	6.10
8.	3,COOH,2,OH,BzG	35.55	dirty white	sint. 190 melt. 230	53.50	4.98	6.40	53.33	4.88	6.22
9.	5,COOH,2,OH,BzG	64.88	white	above 360	53.40	4.67	6.10	53.33	4.88	6.22
10.	6,COOH,2,OH,BzG	45.33	dirty white	220 d	53.20	4.70				6.22

* All m.p.'s are uncorrected.

d = decon

TABLE 2

No.*	methylation product						oxidation product			
	compound	Yield %	colour	m.p.** °C	%N		compound	Yield %	colour	m.p.** °C (lit.)
					Found	Calcd.				
1.	2,OCH ₃ ,BzMG	60.97	dirty yellow	81	6.85	6.69	2,OCH ₃ , benzoic acid	65.28	white	98 (98.5)
2.	2,OCH ₃ ,3,CH ₃ ,BzMG	93.57	brownish yellow	122	6.35	6.27	2,OCH ₃ ,3,CH ₃ , benzoic acid	68.81	faint yellow	85 (85)
3.	2,OCH ₃ ,5,CH ₃ ,BzMG	75.34	brownish yellow	161	6.37	6.27	2,OCH ₃ ,5,CH ₃ , benzoic acid	61.69	faint yellow	69 (69)
4.	2,OCH ₃ ,6,CH ₃ ,BzMG	95.63	light yellow	78	6.16	6.27	2,OCH ₃ ,6,CH ₃ , benzoic acid	59.72	faint yellow	139 (139)
5.	3,Cl,2,OCH ₃ ,BzMG	70.59	brownish red	115	5.64	5.74	3,Cl,2,OCH ₃ , benzoic acid	73.62	faint yellow	117 (117)
6.	5,Cl,2,OCH ₃ ,BzMG	65.48	bright yellow	75	5.62	5.74	5,Cl,2,OCH ₃ , benzoic acid	78.08	faint yellow	81 (81-2)
7.	5,Cl,2,OCH ₃ ,6,CH ₃ ,BzMG	78.69	dirty white	151	5.58	5.43	5,Cl,2,OCH ₃ ,6,CH ₃ , benzoic acid	80.78	faint yellow	142 (--)
8.	3,COOH,2,OCH ₃ ,BzMG	50.73	brown	105	5.60	5.53	2,OCH ₃ , isophthalic acid	55.63	white	216 (216-8)
9.	5,COOH,2,OCH ₃ ,BzMG	54.83	dirty yellow	218	5.53	5.53	4,OCH ₃ , isophthalic acid	59.82	white	275 (275)
10.	6,COOH,2,OCH ₃ ,BzMG	65.12	dirty white	84	5.83	5.53	3,OCH ₃ , phthalic acid	52.78	white	173 (173-4)

* Numbers assigned in accordance with table 1.

** All m.p.'s are uncorrected.

(60–80 ml). The whole was transferred to a separating funnel and poured slowly with stirring in 31 ethanol. The sodium salt of III, separated as white precipitate, was quickly filtered at the pump, washed with 250 ml of ethanol in two portions, sucked as far as possible and then dissolved in water (100–200 ml). The aqueous solution was made acidic to congo red by addition of dil. HCl (50%) with brisk stirring. Thick precipitate of III thus obtained was filtered, washed free of chloride ions with cold water and finally with 50 ml of cold dil. ethanol (25%). N-[2-hydroxy-3 (or 5 or 6)-substituted] benzyl glycines were recrystallised from dil. ethanol.

In the case of *p*-cresol, the viscous reaction mixture was directly poured in water to obtain III which was dissolved in dil. alkali, reprecipitated with dil. HCl, filtered, washed thoroughly with cold water and recrystallised from dil. alcohol. The details of compounds isolated are incorporated in Table 1.

Preparation of N-Methyl-N-[2-methoxy-3 (or 5 or 6)-substituted] benzyl glycines (IV) :

0.03 mole of III was dissolved in 10 ml of 3*N* NaOH in a three necked flask, provided with a mechanical stirrer, a thermometer and two dropping funnels, one for dimethyl sulphate and the other for sodium hydroxide. The solution was heated to 80° on a water bath with stirring. 20 g (15 ml, 0.16 mole) of dimethyl sulphate and 65 ml of 3*N* NaOH were added to the contents of the flask. Dimethyl sulphate was added in small portions (3 ml) at 5 mins. intervals, while the NaOH solution was added at such a rate that the reaction mixture remained slightly alkaline throughout the reaction. After the addition, the reaction mixture was heated at 80° with stirring for further half an hour, finally

cooled and made acidic to congo-red by addition of dil. HCl (50%). The precipitated N-methyl N-[2-methoxy-3 (or 5 or 6)-substituted] benzyl glycines were filtered, washed with cold water till free of sulphate ions. The products were recrystallised from hot water or hot dil. ethanol. The details of alkylation products are furnished in Table 2.

Oxidation of N-Methyl-N-[2-methoxy-3 (or 5 or 6)-substituted] benzyl glycines (IV) :

0.01 mole of (IV) was added to a mixture of 3.3 ml of concentrated HNO₃ (sp. gr. 1.42) and 30 ml of water in a flask. The solution was refluxed for 3 hrs. and cooled in an ice bath. The precipitated methoxy derivatives of benzoic acids (or phthalic acids or isophthalic acids; V) were filtered, washed with cold water and recrystallised from dil. ethanol. These acids were analysed and verified with the help of their authentic samples. The details are furnished in Table 2.

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